

PUPILS' LEARNING BARRIERS AND CLASSROOM BEHAVIOR: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED PUPILS' INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Pupils' Learning Barriers and Classroom Behavior: Basis for a Proposed Pupils' Intervention Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the learning barriers and classroom behavior of Grade Six pupils in H. Bautista Elementary School, Division of Marikina City during the school year 2023-2024. When computed, the summary of the extent to which the pupil respondents experience learning barriers showed that the weighted means for the Emotional, Motivational and Personal Dimensions are 2.38, 2.76 and 2.51, respectively. With an overall weighted mean of 2.55 with verbal interpretation of Moderate. On the other hand, the level of classroom behavior of the pupil respondents as perceived by pupils has an Overall Weighted Mean of 2.96 with a Verbal Interpretation of Moderate. While the teachers' perception has 2.77 which is likewise Moderate. The result after the computation of the Grand Mean is 2.85 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate. Relatively, there is no significant difference between the assessment of the pupils and teacher respondents on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of class participation. More so, 4. The null hypothesis is confirmed, indicating no significant relationship between the learning barriers and classroom behavior. However, there exists a moderate relationship in terms of the motivational factors for classroom behavior. Based on the study's results, an intervention program was deemed necessary and was subsequently proposed.

Keywords: *learning barrier, classroom behavior, intervention program*

Introduction

Behavior problems at school notably interfere with the lesson but also disrupt other pupils. These issues often overwhelm teachers, especially novices, and some consider them the most challenging aspect of a teaching Dulay (2020). Pupils' behavior in the classroom is characterized by various forms, contingent upon the social and cultural context of the school's location. This diversity stems from the multitude of influences that students face in their lives. Some pupils exhibit high activity levels, while others appear disengaged, and still, others remain quiet but manifests themselves differently in their academic pursuits.

Several factors contribute to student engagement in schoolwork and their achievement in academic success. Notably, parental involvement in the child's early education consistently correlates positively with the child's academic performance (Martin & Collie, 2019).

The behavior of students within the classroom significantly influences the overall learning process. Positive behavior fosters good aptitude and social awareness. While negative or disruptive behavior yields adverse effects, not only within the classroom environment, but also on the broader school experience. Students who exhibit such behavior may grasp concepts superficially without truly understanding them, leading to confusion regarding words, meaning, forms, and concepts. Consequently, theories and studies may not be comprehended or applied effectively in real-life situations, resulting in a lack of targeted skill development aligned with daily lesson objectives.

Moreover, pupils' negative or disruptive behavior impedes the teacher's ability to teach effectively necessitating considerable discipline and attention, particularly in a classroom with a large number of pupils. The study aims to elucidate the reasons behind negative behavior through research, actual surveys, and interviews. It seeks to explore interventions for addressing and investigating pupil's negative or destructive behavior.

It has been observed that many pupils nowadays lack focus on their schoolwork, struggling to concentrate on their studies and often failing to complete their homework. According to Okesina (2019), study the causes of poor study habit of pupils include inadequate parental monitoring, parental educational status and laziness. In light of these findings, the researcher was prompted to undertake a study to determine the learning barriers as well as their potential impact on the classroom behavior of learners.

The study focused on the pupils and teachers at H. Bautista Elementary School in Marikina City. This institution was chosen as the subject of the study due to the researcher's personal observation that pupils in this school exhibit learning barriers that effect their classroom behavior and academic performance. By investigating these issues, the study aims to contribute to a better understanding of the challenges students face in their learning environment and to identifying potential strategies for improvement.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the learning barriers and its relationship to the classroom behavior of Grade Six pupils in H. Bautista Elementary School during School Year 2023-2024 to serve as basis for development of an intervention program. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do the pupil respondents experience learning barriers in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 1.1. emotional,

- 1.2. motivational, and
- 1.3. personal?
2. What is the level of classroom behavior of the pupil respondents as assessed by their teachers and pupils themselves in terms of the following variables:
 - 2.1. class participation,
 - 2.2. engagement in group activities,
 - 2.3. listening skills, and
 - 2.4. performance of learning tasks?
3. Is there a significant difference between assessment of the two groups of respondents on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of the aforementioned variables?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the pupils' learning barrier and classroom behavior?
5. What pupils' intervention program may be proposed for an enhanced learning process?

Literature Review

Students' behavior encompasses a broad range of actions, reactions, and conduct within educational settings (Atmojo, 2020). This includes academic engagement, social interactions, emotional expressions, and adherence to school rules and regulations.

As reported, by Gallegos (2020), reasons for students' misbehavior can be categorized into three primary sources: children, teachers, and society. Understanding the interconnections and correlations between the most prevalent misbehaviors in school and their links to broader life experience offers valuable insights into underlying problem patterns (Guariglia, 2019). Addressing the root causes of student misbehavior is crucial for effective problem resolution.

In Smith-Menzies (2023) study, teachers' views on the efficacy and use in behavioral management strategies in school discipline were examined. The research revealed to evidence indicating that punitive disciplinary practices are not only ineffective but also contribute to the marginalization of pupils, especially those from minority and disabled groups.

The study conducted by Araban et al. (2020) investigates the prevalence of factors associated with disruptive behavior among Iranian high school students. Additionally, the study emphasizes the importance of targeting specific constructs associated with disruptive behavior, such as support and stress, for effective prevention and early intervention. The conclusion suggests that health promotion programs focusing on enhancing hopefulness, satisfaction, and support while reducing stress, depression, and smoking may play a vital role in preventing and treating disruptive behavior among youth.

Furthermore, Twardawski and Hilbig (2022) study explored how teachers and 10-year-old students view the treatment of student misbehavior. The study focused on punishment goals—retribution, special prevention, and general prevention. Teachers predominantly favored general prevention, while students leaned towards special prevention and retribution. The divergence was more pronounced in evaluating specific punishment practices than in directly endorsing punishment goals. This study provides valuable insights for crafting intervention strategies to reduce conflicts in teacher-student interactions.

Gurden et al. (2019) conducted a study on emotional and motivational barriers to effective learning in high school students. The hurdles were analyzed from multiple emotional and motivational perspectives, including self-efficacy, self-regulation, lack of professional, parental, or sibling support and guidance, learning environment, and fear of failure, rejection, criticism, judgment, and embarrassment. Based on the study's findings, it appears that pupils struggled with the self-regulatory skill of organizing their study time. A significant learning barrier could be created by instructor support, according to the majority of participant opinions.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive survey method, as outlined by Kothari (2013). Descriptive research aims to define and explore phenomena, including emerging practices, beliefs, ongoing processes, effects, and trends. Survey research involves collecting information from a sample of individuals through their responses to questions (Check & Schutt, 2012, p. 160). Various approaches to participant recruitment, data collection, and instrumentation are possible with this kind of research method. Quantitative analysis such as employing questionnaires with numerically evaluated items, can be utilized in survey research.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were grade six pupils and grade six teachers of Hermogenes Bautista Elementary School. This school has an accessible location at J.P. Rizal St. corner G. Cruz, Concepcion Uno Marikina City. There were 490 students, only 75 or 15% participated along with 17 grade six teachers.

Instrument

This study employed the survey questionnaires to identify learning barriers and their correlation with the classroom behavior of the grade six pupils at H. Bautista Elementary School. Two sets of questionnaires were developed one is the titled, Pupil's Classroom

Behavior Instrument for evaluation by pupils and the teacher's respondents, the other titled, Pupil's Learning barriers and Classroom Behavior Problems as a self-report survey. These questionnaires were adapted and adjusted from the study conducted by Canlog (2016) with modifications subjected to validation by six experts from different schools, including guidance counselors and master teachers. The finalized questionnaire served as the primary tool for collecting the data from both pupil and teacher respondents.

Procedure

Before administering the questionnaire to grade six pupils, the researcher initially conducted purposive survey interviews, engaging in formal conversations and inquiries with all grade six teachers. This aimed to identify which pupils were most suitable for the study based on teachers' recommendations, considering their observations of students' behavior during class hours and anecdotal records of their learning performance.

Subsequently, the researcher prepared all the necessary communications to relevant authorities regarding the study's conduct. Letters of request to conduct the study were provided to the Principal of H. Bautista Elementary School, and these communications were personally presented by the researcher to the school heads to facilitate the administration of the questionnaires. Additionally, letters of consent for the pupil respondents and their parents were issued to seek permission for their participation in the research. The data-gathering instrument was directly distributed to all the respondents and retrieved once completed. The gathered data were tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted accordingly.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations including voluntary participation, informed consent anonymity, and confidentiality, were prepared by the researcher to protect the rights of respondents, ensure research validity and maintain scientific integrity.

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Results and Discussion

Extent of the Pupil Respondents Experience Learning Barriers

Table 1. *Extent of the Pupil Respondents' Experience of Learning Barriers in Terms of Emotional*

Indicators	Pupils	
	Mean	Verbal
1. I experience love-related problems.	2.75	M
2. I have parental conflicts.	1.92	L
3. I have conflicts with my teachers.	1.77	L
4. I have conflict with my peers.	2.48	L
5. I experience self-related problem such as self-pity, insecurities etc.	2.96	M
Overall Weighted Mean	2.38	Low
Standard Deviation	0.64	

As presented in the table, the extent to which the pupils respondents experience learning barriers in terms of emotional disagreement is Low as perceived by the student's respondents, as evidenced by an overall weighted mean of 2.38. The data implies that the extent of the pupils' experience of learning barriers in terms of emotional was Low. However, there are some indicators, that can be help through proposed intervention. According to Touvinen et al. (2020), addressing these obstacles is crucial for fostering a positive and supportive school climate conducive to effective learning and emotional well-being. Because of these, the schools and educators, recognizing the significance will play a pivotal role in implementing evidence-based intervention strategies to support students facing these challenges.

Table 2. *Extent of the Pupil Respondents' Experience of Learning Barriers in Terms of Motivational*

Indicators	Pupils	
	Mean	Verbal
1. I often lack previous knowledge of the lesson.	2.72	M
2. I lack focus in my studies.	2.72	M
3. I am afraid of failure.	3.39	M
4. I lack confidence in my abilities.	2.72	M
5. I lack motivation or interest in the subject matter.	2.35	L
Overall Weighted Mean	2.76	Moderate
Standard Deviation	0.87	

As presented in the table, the extent to which the pupil respondents experience learning barriers in terms of motivational as perceived

by students has a 2.76, overall weighted mean by interpretation of moderate with standard deviation of 0.87. The data imply that the extent of the pupils' experience of learning barriers in terms of motivational was moderate. Moving beyond disruptive behaviors, motivational obstacles, like a lack of interest or perceived relevance in academic tasks, hinder students' engagement and performance (Anderman, 2019). Based on this study, there are some experiences where learning barriers are slightly affected in the pupil's responses in terms of motivational, on the other hand, it helps some interventions that may be proposed.

Table 3. Extent of the Pupil Respondents' Experience of Learning Barriers in Terms of Personal

Indicators	Pupils	
	Mean	Verbal
1. I am part of a broken family.	2.56	M
2. I am abused by my family member(s)- verbally, physically and sexually	2.28	L
3. I experience bullying inside the school.	3.12	M
4. I find ways to earn money to help my family financially (ex. selling goods, products, recyclables, etc)	3.05	M
5. I engage into gambling.	1.72	L
6. My allowance is not enough for food and school fees.	2.13	L
7. I do cut classes	1.89	L
8. I am teased by another's name.	2.53	M
9. I make noise and unnecessary remarks.	2.73	M
10. I engage into side conversations or gossips.	3.05	M
Overall Weighted Mean	2.51	Moderate
Standard Deviation	0.43	

As presented in the table, the extent to which the pupil respondents experience learning barriers in terms of personal as perceived by pupils has overall weighted mean of 2.51 with verbal interpretation of Moderate (M) with standard Deviation of 0.43. The data imply that the extent of the pupils' experience of learning barriers in terms of personal factors was moderate. Therefore, the learners must have a conducive learning environment and better appropriate learning activities that are necessary for a meaningful educational experience and prevent such behaviors effectively.

Level of Classroom Behavior of the Pupil Respondents as assessed by the Teachers and Pupils

Table 4. Level of Classroom Behavior of the Pupil Respondents in terms of Class Participation

Indicators	Pupils		Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. Interrupts the teacher during discussions	2.17	L	2.91	M
2. daydream and inattentive in class	2.69	M	3.12	M
3. always do their assignment and come prepared in class	3.65	H	2.41	L
4. confidently raise their hand to answer discussion questions	3.65	H	2.62	M
5. is very eager and excited come to class at all time	3.56	H	2.88	M
Weighted Mean	3.15	M	2.79	M
Overall Weighted Mean	2.97- Moderate			
Standard Deviation	0.54		0.55	

As presented in Table 6, the level of classroom behavior of the pupils' respondents as assessed by their teachers and the pupils themselves in terms of class participation. The pupil's perception is 3.15 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate (M), and the teacher's perception is 2.79 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate (M) in terms of class participation with standard deviation of 0.54 and 0.55 respectively. This resulted in an overall weighted mean of 2.97 with a verbal interpretation is Moderate (M). The data imply that both pupils and teachers had the same perfectives, with a moderate level of classroom behavior among the pupils as assessed by their teachers and the pupils themselves in terms of class participation.

Table 5. Level of Classroom Behavior of the Pupil Respondents in terms of Engagement in Group Activities

Indicators	Pupils		Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. prefer to work alone than with group	2.31	L	2.49	L
2. get bored easily in doing Group Activities	2.07	L	2.80	M
3. often volunteered to lead the group	2.96	M	2.26	L
4. often engaged in disputes and disagreement with the group	2.71	M	2.61	M
5. easily get along well with a group	3.08	M	2.79	M
Weighted Mean	2.62	M	2.59	M
Overall Weighted Mean	2.60- Moderate			
Standard Deviation	0.64		0.49	

As presented in the table, the level of classroom behavior of the students as assessed by the pupils themselves computed a weighted

mean of 2.62 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate (M). And Teachers is computed at 2.59 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate (M) in terms of engagement in group activities. This resulted in an overall weighted mean of 2.60 with the verbal interpretation of Moderate (M) respectively.

The data imply that both pupils and teachers somewhat agree that engagement in group activities, such as preferring to work alone rather than with the group, getting bored easily in doing group activities, often engaging in disputes and disagreements with the group, and easily getting along well with a group, pupils and teachers are equally of the same perspective, and also the result of the table shows that both students and teachers' points of view were homogenous.

Table 6. Level of Classroom Behavior of the Pupil Respondents in terms of Listening

Indicators	Pupils		Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. tend to forget the rules in listening	2.81	M	3.05	M
2. can easily comprehend what they listen to	2.95	M	2.80	M
3. ignore what they listen to	2.39	L	2.85	M
4. clearly remember the details of what they listen to	3.48	H	2.80	M
5. can get easily annoyed by any distractions when listening.	3.08	M	3.23	M
Weighted Mean	2.94	M	2.95	M
Overall Weighted Mean	2.94- Moderate			
Standard Deviation	0.50		0.51	

As presented in Table 6, the level of classroom behavior of the student-respondents as assessed by the pupils and teachers in terms of listening skills is that the pupils perceived a overall weighted mean of 2.94, verbally interpretation as Moderate (M). The teacher's respondent perceived a weighted mean of 2.95 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate (M). This resulted in an overall weighted mean of 2.94, verbally interpretation of Moderate (M) and the standard deviation of pupils and teachers perceived is 0.50 and 0.51 respectively.

The data imply that two groups of respondents have coincided with the same result, with the overall weighted mean of moderate. Therefore, pupils' and teachers' perspectives on listening skills moderately affect classroom behavior.

Table 7. Level of Classroom Behavior of the Pupil Respondents in terms of Performance Learning Tasks

Indicators	Pupils		Teachers	
	M	VI	M	VI
1. perform poorly in performance tasks	2.67	M	3.12	M
2. find practical application in what they have learned to real life situation.	3.45	M	2.80	M
3. I have habitual tardiness and absenteeism that affects my performance.	2.45	L	2.84	M
4. I diligently follow the criteria in performing learning tasks.	3.67	H	2.62	M
5. practice collaboration and sharing of ideas in accomplishing a task.	3.48	H	3.45	L
Weighted Mean	3.14	M	2.77	M
Overall Weighted Mean	2.95- Moderate			
Standard Deviation	0.51		0.41	

As presented in the table, the level of classroom behavior of the pupils's respondents as assessed by the students and teachers in terms of performance learning tasks. The pupils perceived a weighted mean of 3.14. with the verbal interpretation of moderate (M), The teacher's respondent perceived a weighted mean of 2.77 with a verbal interpretation of Moderate (M). This resulted in an overall weighted mean of 2.95 with a verbal interpretation of moderate (M).

The data imply that both pupils' and teachers' perceptions of performance learning tasks are remarkably moderate. Therefore, both pupils' and teachers' performance in learning tasks notably shows that there is a connection in terms of classroom behavior.

Test of Significant Difference Between the agreement of the in the two groups of Respondents on the level of Pupils' Classroom Behavior

Table 8. Test of Significant Difference Between the Assessment of Pupils and Teacher on Pupils level Behavior in terms of Class Participation

Respondents	Mean	P value	Decision	Interpretation
1. Pupils	3.16	0.99	Failed to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
2. Teachers	2.74			

Since the computed p-value of 0.98 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the assessment of pupils and teachers on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of engagement in group activities. The data reveal that both pupils and teachers have the same perceptions of the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of engagement in group activities.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Assessment of Pupils and Teacher on Pupils level Behavior in terms of Learning Skills*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Pupils	2.90	0.14	Failed to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
2. Teachers	2.95			

Since the computed p-value of 0.14 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between assessment of pupils and teachers on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of learning skills. The data reveal that both pupils and teachers have the same perceptions on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of learning skills.

Table 10. *Test of Significant Difference Between the Assessment of Pupils Teacher on Pupils level Behavior in terms of Performance Tasks*

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
1. Pupils	3.13	1.00	Failed to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
2. Teachers	2.77			

Since the computed p-value of 1.00 is greater than the 5% level of significance, the null hypothesis is confirmed. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the assessment of pupils and teachers on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of performance tasks. The data reveal that both pupils and teachers have the same perceptions on the level of pupils' classroom behavior in terms of performance tasks.

Table 11. *Test of Significant Relationship in terms of Emotional*

<i>Emotional</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
a. Class participation	-0.077	Negligible	0.56	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
b. Engagement in Group Activities	0.175	Weak	0.18	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
c. Listening Skills	-0.323	Negligible	0.12	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
d. Performance Learning Tasks	-0.069	Negligible	0.60	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant

These data revealed that the involvement of emotional barriers in the classroom behavior of pupils remarkably proved that there is no connection in terms of class participation, performance of learning tasks, or listening skills. On other hand, engagement in group activities was weak and nearly affected the relationship also considered that there are ways to help improve the pupil's participation in group activities. Even though the relationships are considered insignificant, these data show that the emotional barriers of the pupils could help them in their classroom behavior.

Table 12. *Test of Significant Relationship in terms of Motivational*

<i>Motivational</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
a. Class participation	-0.159	Negligible	0.22	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
b. Engagement in Group Activities	0.091	Negligible	0.49	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
c. Listening Skills	-0.196	Negligible	0.13	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
d. Performance Learning Tasks	-0.223	Weak	0.87	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant

These data revealed that the emotional barriers in the classroom behavior of pupils in terms of motivational notably proved that three indicators, class participation, engagement in group activities, or listening skills are considered insignificant. On the other hand, the performance of learning tasks was weak. Therefore, the relationships between each indicator are considered important; however, these data have shown that the emotional barriers of the pupils could help them in their classroom behavior in terms of motivational.

Table 13. *Test of Significant Relationship in terms of Personal*

<i>Personal</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
a. Class participation	0.062	Negligible	0.64	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
b. Engagement in Group Activities	0.059	Negligible	0.65	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
c. Listening Skills	-0.074	Negligible	0.57	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
d. Performance Learning Tasks	0.091	Negligible	0.49	Fail to Reject H ₀	Not Significant

These data revealed that the personal barriers to the in-classroom behavior of pupils remarkably showed classroom participation, listening skills, performance of learning tasks, and engagement in group activities coincided. The interpretation connects to the classroom behavior of students' class participation, listening skills, and performance of learning tasks. The relationships are considered the same as each other; however, these data have shown that the barriers mentioned could help the students in their classroom behavior in terms of personal.

Proposed Intervention Program

I. Rationale

Anything that keeps a learner from participating completely in the process of learning is a barrier to learning. A person, or even a group of people, affected by learning barriers feels frustrated or unwilling, and cannot achieve their learning goals (Green, 2023)

In this study, the barriers to learning such as emotional, motivational and personal are given emphasis. Emotional barriers are those that pertain to being afraid of failing or could also include someone's past insecurities, or fear of change that can ignite uncomfortable emotional states preventing learners from taking full advantage of the learning opportunities in front of them. Motivational barriers on the other hand, include a lack of goals or purpose. The learners have the tendency to become less inclined in absorbing information when a lesson doesn't seem to fit their interest. Whereas personal-socio economic barriers involve learners that are strapped for their learning resources that restrict them to one learning style that might not be the best for them.

The researcher also investigates pupils' classroom behaviors such as class participation, engagement in group activities, listening skills, and performance of learning tasks. Understanding the classroom behavior of pupils is very crucial in shaping an effective learning environment for them.

To improve learning engagement, stakeholders must understand the classroom behaviors of pupils, and help mitigate learning barriers, the researcher hereby proposes a six-month pupils' Intervention Program to address these concerns as it relates to the learning process.

II. Objectives

This program is intended for pupils who have difficulty coping with learning barriers and to help improve their classroom performance and behavior. Specifically, this aims to:

1. Address each student's specific area of need.
2. Nurturing, a safe environment, which can positively contribute to the pupil's overall well-being.
3. Engage in collaboration and understand new or existing factors of learning barriers through discussion during class.
4. Aim to achieve high performance in all regards.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, several conclusions were drawn. Firstly, the barriers related to pupils' emotional, motivational, and personal dimensions can significantly impact their well-being and academic performance. Both pupils and teachers equally recognize that class participation, engagement in group activities, listening skills, and performance of learning tasks play a crucial role in shaping pupils' classroom behavior. Additionally, it was observed that both students and teachers share similar perceptions regarding the level of students' classroom behavior, particularly in terms of class participation. However, there appears to be little connection between the identified learning barriers and classroom behavior, suggesting that while these barriers affect well-being and academic outcomes, they may not directly influence how students behave in the classroom setting.

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